

Extractive spectrophotometric method for benomyl adsorption in soils

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Abstract : An extractive spectrophotometric method for benomyl adsorption in soils has been developed. The method is based on the microwave assisted alkaline hydrolysis of the fungicide to carbendazim and *n*-butylamine and the colour reaction of the latter with carbon disulphide and copper(I) perchlorate to form chloroform extractable brownish yellow copper(I) *n*-butyldithiocarbamate showing maximum absorbance at 360 nm. The colour is stable for at least 2 h and the fungicide concentration can be determined with a maximum relative standard deviation of 1.0%. The adsorption isotherms of benomyl on four soils of different characteristics have been evaluated by Freundlich's adsorption equation followed by evaluation of its leaching potential in terms of ground water ubiquity score (GUS). The GUS has been found in the range 0.3–0.4, classifying it as a nonleacher pesticide.

Keywords : Benomyl, microwave assisted hydrolysis, soil adsorption study.

Introduction

Benomyl (methyl 1-(butylcarbamoyl)-2-benzimidazole-carbamate) is one of the important benzimidazolic systemic fungicides used to control a wide range of fungal diseases¹. It has various adverse effects on non target organisms and has been classified as hazardous to human health^{1–5}. Applied pesticides will in one way or other end up in soil or water bodies. Soil curtails mobility of pesticide chemicals in two ways : by sorption and by biological or chemical degradation⁶. Increasing amounts of research revealed that sorption is a key process for deciding the ultimate fate of pesticide in terms of transport, persistence, bioactivity and consequently mobility and extent of surface and ground water contamination.

Various analytical methods developed for the analysis of benomyl viz. liquid chromatography^{7,8}, HPLC^{9,10}, gas chromatography¹¹, spectrofluometry¹², flowinjection¹³ and densitometric¹⁴ are mostly based on its conversion to methyl 2-benzimidazole carbamate (MBC) commonly known as carbendazim or 2-aminobenzimidazole (2-AB) by acid/base hydrolysis. These methods require number

of steps with strict adherence to experimental conditions during the hydrolysis of the fungicide, thus making the methods tedious and time consuming. On the other hand, liquid chromatographic methods are expensive. In view of above we have developed a simple, sensitive and reliable extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination benomyl in commercial formulations and study its adsorption in soils to evaluate its leaching potential in terms of groundwater ubiquity scores.

Results and discussion

The proposed method is based on the colour reaction of *n*-butylamine, one of the microwave assisted hydrolytic products of benomyl, with carbon disulphide and copper(I) perchlorate in acetonitrile, to form a chloroform extractable brownish yellow copper(I) butyldithiocarbamate complex. That benomyl on hydrolysis forms MBC and *n*-butylamine and the later react with carbon disulphide and copper(I) to form yellow copper(I) dithiocarbamate are quite well known^{15,16}. To assess the validity of the proposed method in soil adsorption study the effect of various common ions on the determination of

fungicide was studied and it was found that most of the common ions viz. Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , PO_4^{3-} and acetate present in the soil do not interfere in the proposed method. Under the optimised experimental conditions, the proposed extractive spectrophotometric method obeys Beer's law in the range 4.85–72.57 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of benomyl solution. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $2.615 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.1112 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

The adsorption isotherms of benomyl on four soils of different soil characteristics (Table 1) were evaluated by Freundlich's adsorption eq. (1).

$$X = K_f C_e^{n_f} \quad (1)$$

where X is the amount of pesticide adsorbed mg kg^{-1} of the adsorbent; C_e is the equilibrium concentration in so-

Table 1. Characteristics of the different Indian soils used in the adsorption study of benomyl

Soil sample	pH	Clay (%)	Organic carbon (%)	Cation Exchange Capacity (meq/100 g)
I	7.2	32.6	0.8	13.1
II	7.6	18.2	0.9	12.9
III	6.5	20.0	1.5	11.0
IV	6.8	23.4	1.6	12.8

lution (mg L^{-1}); K_f and n_f are adsorption coefficients which are calculated from the least square methods applied to the linear form of the Freundlich's adsorption eq. (2) by the plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ (Fig. 1).

$$\log X = \log K_f + n_f \log C_e \quad (2)$$

The various adsorption parameters viz. soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}), Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) and groundwater ubiquity score (GUS) have been calculated by using eqs. (3-6) respectively¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and are given in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ for the evaluation of Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f for benomyl.

Table 2. Adsorption parameters for the adsorption of benomyl fungicide on four Indian soils

Soil	K_f	n_f	K_d	K_{oc}	ΔG°	GUS
I	43.65	0.661	17.86	2232	-7.142	0.31
II	42.22	0.699	19.02	2113	-7.298	0.32
III	47.21	0.729	24.55	1637	-7.932	0.37
IV	46.51	0.748	25.29	1581	-8.005	0.38

$$K_d = \frac{X}{C_e} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_d \quad (4)$$

$$K_{oc} = K_d \times \left(\frac{100}{\%OC} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{GUS} = \log t_{1/2} [4 - \log(K_{oc})] \quad (6)$$

where R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature, $t_{1/2}$ = pesticide persistence (half life), OC = organic carbon content of soil.

The isotherms are used for identifying the nature of adsorption of solutes from aqueous solutions. The iso-

therms obtained for benomyl are almost L-type²⁰ representing a relatively high affinity between the solid surface and solute which is further supported by value of $n_f < 1$ (Table 2). Higher values of K_f also favour the adsorption phenomena and consequently lower the tendency of pesticide to move in soil. The organic matter content and the clay content of soils also play a very important role in the sorption of pesticides as these components provide soils with an increased number of adsorptive sites onto which pesticides molecules can bind²¹. Another soil parameter i.e. cation exchange capacity (CEC) which is directly proportional to hydrophobic nature of adsorbent also affects the adsorption process. Benomyl being more hydrophobic exhibit higher adsorption affinity for the soils with higher CEC. The higher K_d values of benomyl with all soil types further substantiates the greater benomyl adsorption. The K_{OC} is less soil specific and is calculated by normalising K_d with the organic carbon (OC) content of the soil²². The high values of K_{OC} also suggest that benomyl is strongly adsorbed to soils. The negative value of Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) for the adsorption of benomyl suggests that the adsorption process is energetically favourable. The leaching potential of fungicide was evaluated in terms of GUS index which has been determined by using experimentally observed K_{OC} value for each soil sample and literature reported half life of benomyl³. The GUS values for benomyl (0.31–0.38) are below 1.8, which classifies it as a non-leacher pesticide²³.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments :

Acetonitrile (Merck, AR) was kept over phosphorus pentoxide (5 g L^{-1}) and distilled twice. The analytical standard of benomyl (Sigma-Aldrich Labochemikalien GmbH, Germany) was used and its stock solution ($10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) was prepared in acetonitrile. Copper(I) perchlorate and its standard solution (0.01 mol L^{-1} in acetonitrile) was prepared by the reported method²⁴. To a hot solution of hydrated copper(II) perchlorate in acetonitrile an excess of copper powder (99.9% pure) was added and solution stirred vigorously. When whole copper(II) perchlorate got converted into copper(I) perchlorate, the solution became colourless. The solution was then quickly

filtered while hot. On cooling, white crystals of copper(I) perchlorate separate out. The salt was recrystallised from anhydrous acetonitrile and dried under vacuum. Its standard solution was prepared by dissolving a little more than the calculated amount of the compound in acetonitrile and standardized by titration with ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) in 1 N sulphuric acid medium using ferroin as indicator. A 2% solution of carbon disulphide (Merck, AR) in acetonitrile was used. Sodium bicarbonate (CDH, LR), its $\approx 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ aqueous solution was used. The soils used in the adsorption study were collected from Solan District of Himachal Pradesh, India.

All the spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Spectronic 20D⁺ spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells. Domestic microwave oven, Samsung, was used for microwave assisted hydrolysis.

Preparation of calibration graph for pure compound :

Aliquots (0.1–2.0 mL) of standard solution of benomyl ($10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile) were taken in 10 mL measuring flasks and volume made to 2.0 mL with acetonitrile. Each solution was mixed with 1 mL aqueous sodium bicarbonate ($\approx 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) solution, 0.5 mL of 2% carbon disulphide (in acetonitrile) and 1.5 mL of distilled water and kept in the microwave oven for 40 s and allowed to stand for 15 min. The hydrolyzed benomyl solution was then mixed with copper(I) perchlorate (1 mL, 0.01 mol L^{-1}). Each mixture solution was equilibrated with 4 mL of chloroform for five minutes. The chloroform layer was separated, volume made to 6 mL with chloroform and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (1.5 g) and the absorbance measured at 360 nm against a reagent blank and a calibration graph was prepared (Fig. 2).

Soil adsorption study :

Benomyl adsorption isotherms on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics (Table 1) were obtained by the batch equilibration technique using 50 mL conical flask. Triplicate soil samples (2.0 g) were equilibrated with aqueous-acetonitrile benomyl solutions in the concentration range from 43.5–101.6 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ by shaking in Incubator Shaker PT-422 at room temperature ($25 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for 12 h equilibrium time. After equilibration, the sus-

Fig. 2. Calibration graph of benomyl.

pensions were centrifuged and the equilibrium concentrations (C_e) were determined in supernatants by the spectrophotometric procedure described above.

Conclusion

The proposed method for the determination of benomyl is simple, rapid and reliable and is of wide applicability. Adsorption studies of benomyl indicate that it is strongly adsorbed on to soils and this consequently inhibits its penetration into water sources. This is further supported by groundwater ubiquity score (GUS) which is below 1.8, classifying it as a non-leacher pesticide and hence it does not represent hazard to ground water contamination.

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